

8T – The Coupling Constants Series and EMT Symmetry

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series under shifting generation, i.e. the electron with the Muon or the Tau, the author will argue for additional symmetry which preserves the magnitude of each coupling term. What is varying is the energy of the net curvature, i.e. the photon in the case of the third coupling term.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor M , given by the conditions on (1.1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures and so flatten each other, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21).

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.3) to (1.34) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.43)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up to this point reader is familiar with those equations. Now suppose that the electron has absorbed a discrete amount of net curvature, its energy increased. Since we are familiar with the equivalence relation between mass and energy, as presented by Albert Einstein, energy increase is synonymous with mass increase. Suppose its mass increased in such way that now instead of the electron, it is a Muon or a Tau.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

In addition, the Tau:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.46)$$

Mass is curvature converging inward, so if the electron has absorbed net curvature its mass increased. That is supported by the Quark masses series of the 8T. Those higher generation particle according to coupling series are representing a symmetry. The magnitude will stay as it is, invariantly of the actual particle, we can call it the EMT symmetry, first letter of each generation particle name. What will vary as a result of the particle varied is energy of the photon emitted.

The heavier the particle, the more energy the emitted net curvature should contain. That is again implied by equivalence between mass and energy. Such a construction allow us to make two predictions regarding the energy of the net curvature, i.e. the photon in the case of the third coupling term:

- (1) The Energy of the photon emitted is proportional to Lepton generation.
- (2) The coupling constants series is invariant to generation – what is varying is the energy of the net curvature.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)